

Cluster trials inference with CARE

Keywords: cluster-robust inference | cluster-randomised clinical trials | model robustness | jackknife variance estimator | assumption sensitivity | pragmatic design

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We show that cluster-randomised trials—especially pragmatic designs—often exhibit substantial (but underappreciated in practice) heterogeneity in cluster sizes and structures, distorting inference. Our simulations—reassigning treatment in real data and varying imbalance in synthetic data—show that currently recommended methods (such as targeted maximum likelihood estimation and small-sample corrected generalised estimating equations) are not optimised to this challenge. We propose the CARE (Clarify, Apply, Refine, Evaluate) protocol, which anchors inference in a design-based benchmark and provides a principled pathway for incorporating assumption-rich methods—making trial analysis more credible, transparent, and directly comparable across studies.

1. Introduction

Cluster-randomised trials (CRTs), in which entire groups (such as hospitals, schools, or communities) are randomised rather than individuals, have become a mainstay of public health and clinical research. Their popularity has surged over the past 15 years, with a tenfold increase in usage [1–4], driven by their logistical advantages, broad applicability, and strong external validity. This growth is particularly evident in pragmatic CRTs. Data from ClinicalTrials.gov show that annual CRT registrations rose from 30 in 2009 to 196 in 2019. Over a similar period, the proportion classified as pragmatic rose from about 1% in 2007 to nearly 15% in the most recent year examined, reflecting their expanding role in real-world clinical research.

While CRT designs have grown increasingly pragmatic and complex, the analytical methods used for their evaluation have largely remained unchanged. Ideally, methodological innovation would have kept pace with the evolution of trial design. The clinical-trials literature has recognised the potential of approaches such as targeted maximum likelihood estimation (TMLE), valued for robustness to model misspecification and flexibility with complex data [5]. Yet despite this theoretical support, uptake has been minimal: its technical demands, limited software support (R only), and complex tuning mean most analysts continue to rely on traditional methods.

Recent methodological reviews of CRTs consistently report reliance on a narrow range of conventional statistical approaches. Across studies, approximately 65% use generalised linear mixed-effects models (GLMEs), 25% apply generalised estimating equations (GEEs), and about 10% fail to account for within-cluster correlation altogether [1–4]. This trend, repeatedly noted in the literature [1–4], reflects a practical ceiling: even established methods such as GLMEs and GEEs require careful specification and substantial expertise. Consequently, adoption of newer estimators like TMLE has been limited because current practice already strains technical capacity.

Significance Statement

Cluster-randomised trials are increasingly pragmatic, but accessible analytic tools have not kept pace. Advanced estimators such as targeted maximum likelihood estimation offer appealing theory yet remain demanding to implement, while conventional approaches such as generalised linear mixed-effects models and generalised estimating equations with small-sample corrections can be unstable or assumption-dependent. Through simulations using real and synthetic data, we show how these limitations distort inference in realistic datasets. We introduce CARE, a simple protocol combining model-agnostic diagnostics with a design-based default, to make trial analysis more credible, transparent, and scalable. As regulators increasingly accommodate Bayesian approaches, CARE provides the missing infrastructure: not a prohibition on sophisticated methods, but a structured framework that requires them to be justified against a robust benchmark, bridging econometric and clinical-trial practice.

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These issues become even more pronounced in the era of pragmatic trials. In clinical research, there is no precise analytical definition of a ‘pragmatic’ trial, but the term is generally understood to imply a deliberate relaxation of certain elements of the traditional experimental framework, while still maintaining randomisation [6]. Pragmatic CRTs are often easier to implement than tightly controlled efficacy trials, which partly explains their growing popularity. However, this same relaxation of design constraints makes them more difficult to evaluate. As a result, a widening gap has emerged between the operational simplicity of pragmatic trials and the escalating analytical complexity required to make sense of them.

Table 1. Pragmatic and quasi-experimental designs

	Classical experiments	Quasi-experiments
Design knowledge	Full	Partial
Sample size	Smaller	Larger
Data cost	High	Low
Primary focus	Efficiency	Robustness
Assumptions	Strong	Minimal
External validity	Limited	Maximal

Notes: Pragmatic CRTs relax classical trial constraints, increasingly resembling quasi-experiments in structure, scale, and analytical demands. A similar contrast—between explanatory (‘classical’) and pragmatic (‘quasi-experimental’) trials—is summarised in Table 1 of [6].

Importantly, the quasi-experimental literature has developed well-established, reliable practices for handling complex within-cluster correlations. These methods, grounded in classical statistical theory [e.g., 7–14] and honed through decades of applied use, provide clear guidelines [15–17] and simple, computationally stable tools that avoid reliance on specialised software or advanced programming skills.

Building on this, we argue that rather than steering trialists toward increasingly complex estimators reliant on fragile computational pipelines, there is real value in adopting proven tools and practices from quasi-experimental research. To this end, we propose a simple, extensible framework that integrates these methods into a standard trial Statistical Analysis Plan (**SAP**), making them accessible, scalable, and transparent. We call this framework CARE—Clarify, Apply, Refine, Evaluate. The ‘R’ is silent, much like in non-rhotic varieties of English such as Australian and many British dialects, emphasising its optional role in the analysis process.

Traditional SAPs in CRTs typically move from protocol to simulation and then to evaluation—as illustrated in Figure 1 with the dashed arrow—relying heavily on assumptions baked into design-stage models. But trial data (especially in pragmatic settings) often depart from these assumptions in ways that are only revealed post hoc. Simulations, while useful, are by definition detached from the actual data. CARE addresses this gap through four steps.

First, Clarify the observed data structure: use deletion-based influence diagnostics—via the `summclust` package in R and Stata [18]—to characterise cluster leverage, partial leverage, and leave-one-cluster-out effects before drawing inferences. These tools surface heterogeneity that standard summaries such as the intraclass correlation coefficient (**ICC**) can obscure. Second, Apply a default, design-anchored analysis using cluster-robust generalised linear models (**GLMs**) with identity or log links and cluster-robust variance (**CV**) estimation—specifically CV3, the leave-one-cluster-out jackknife—providing a low-assumption benchmark across continuous, binary, and count outcomes in standard software. Third, Refine allows, but does not require, extensions using alternative (e.g., randomisation inference) or assumption-rich approaches (e.g., GEE, GLME, Bayesian, TMLE) when motivated and computationally stable. Finally, Evaluate synthesises the outputs: Apply and any Refine results are reported side by side, and when they disagree the burden of justification falls on the assumption-rich refinement in light of the Clarify diagnostics.

This paper offers a shift in perspective. Pragmatic CRTs, by relaxing key elements of classical trial design, increasingly resemble quasi-experimental studies—where limited control, structural complexity, and messy data are the norm. Unlike pragmatic trials, quasi-experiments have long been analytically defined and studied within a dedicated methodological tradition. As shown in Table 1, these designs typically involve partial design knowledge, larger samples, lower data costs, and a prioritisation of robustness over efficiency. Many of these same features now appear in pragmatic CRTs, even as they retain randomisation at their core [6].

Notes: Traditional trial workflows move directly from simulations to evaluation (dashed arrow). The CARE extension inserts two mandatory steps—Clarify and Apply—between simulation and evaluation, with an optional sensitivity layer (Refine).

2. Modelling or allowing dependence

In clinical trial evaluation, the goal is typically to estimate a causal effect—some hypothetical quantity that represents the difference in patient outcomes had the treatment been delivered versus not. This target quantity, or causal estimand, is defined by clinical theory and motivates the trial design. In most cases, the estimand corresponds to an average treatment effect across individuals or clusters [19].

Estimators such as GEE, GLME, and, more recently, TMLE are commonly proposed in CRTs to approximate this quantity from data. Though these approaches differ—GEE yields population-averaged effects, GLME gives cluster-specific estimates, and TMLE allows either—the distinctions are usually negligible under randomisation. For clinical interpretation and theoretical exposition alike, they all target the same estimand. Randomisation guarantees an unbiased estimation of the treatment effect. As a result, the main inferential challenge shifts from modelling the mean to correctly capturing the variance-covariance matrix (**VCM**), which encodes dependence between observations. It is here (in modelling or allowing for dependence) that the most consequential decisions for inference in CRTs are made.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \phi & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \phi & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \phi & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \phi & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \phi_1^A & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \phi_2^B & a_{12}^B & a_{13}^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{21}^B & \phi_3^B & a_{23}^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{31}^B & a_{32}^B & \phi_4^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \phi_5^C & a_{12}^C \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & a_{21}^C & \phi_6^C \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The left-hand matrix (1) represents an analytically convenient but empirically rare case of independent and identically distributed (**iid**) data. In this matrix, all observations are independent, as shown by the zeros in off-diagonal positions. For example, the first line indicates that the first observation does not correlate with observations 2 to 6. Additionally, the covariances are identical (homoskedastic) for each observation and of magnitude ϕ .

If this were the true uncertainty structure in the data, then, for example, an identity link GLM, which is also an ordinary least squares (**OLS**) estimator under the classical assumption of normally distributed error terms, would be appropriate. This OLS uncertainty structure, also called spherical, assumes the covariance ϕ is the same for each observation. This makes OLS efficient, as it uses all the information extracted from the data to estimate a single parameter assumed to capture uncertainty sufficiently.

For some traditional trials, where each design aspect is tightly controlled and data are carefully selected to align with specific variance structures, VCMs like this could be plausible. In such highly controlled settings, where researchers intentionally shape the study design and data collection to conform to simpler variance structures, OLS with spherical errors is appealing, as it delivers the smallest standard errors and exact confidence intervals.

In contrast, in CRTs, the iid assumption is usually violated in two ways. Examine the right-hand matrix (2), which illustrates what a VCM for a contemporary CRT might look like. In this case, we have six observations from three clusters: A, B, and C. Firstly, we see a violation of the identically distributed assumption. On the main diagonal, all the ϕ_i elements have unique subscripts, indicating that each observation varies in its own idiosyncratic way and that the data are heteroskedastic. Secondly, we observe a violation of independence. Observing the second line, we see that observation 2 correlates with observations 3 and 4—evidenced by a_{12}^B and a_{13}^B —due to their shared cluster B. Note also that the clusters are unbalanced, exhibiting different sizes.

The problem arises when we use, for example, OLS and a spherical VCM. Such a model disregards the extent of uncertainty shown in the right-hand matrix (2), instead assuming a simplistic structure like that in the left-hand matrix (1). This misrepresentation of uncertainty leads to an overestimation of the information content in the data, resulting in false statistical significance. This issue persists even when different link functions are used, such as the

log or logit (corresponding to Poisson or logistic regression, respectively), as selecting a different link function alters the scale of parameters ϕ while still assuming the VCM structure similar to the left-hand matrix (1) where violation of independence is neglected.

The complex structure illustrated in the right-hand matrix (2) is what is understood as cluster heterogeneity—the combination of structural differences between clusters. The key components of cluster heterogeneity visible in the matrix are: (H1) heterogeneity in variance (heteroskedasticity), where the diagonal ϕ_i terms are unique to each observation; (H2) heterogeneity in size, as implied by the different block sizes for clusters A, B, and C; and (H3) heterogeneity in correlation structures. This last feature is seen in the off-diagonal parameters (e.g., α_{13}^B), which capture idiosyncratic correlations unique to each cluster, as denoted by the superscripts.

In pragmatic CRTs, the challenge of managing cluster heterogeneity is compounded by two additional realities. First, there is (H4) uncertainty in the correlation structure itself. The real-world focus of pragmatic trials means that these complex correlation patterns are not only present but often unpredictable. Second, contemporary CRTs frequently involve (H5) a limited number of clusters, which amplifies the difficulty of making robust statistical inferences.

The central question becomes: what is the appropriate regression-based method to accommodate these complex and potentially unknown correlations, as highlighted in the right-hand matrix (2)? We postulate that pragmatic designs call for what might be termed a pragmatic estimator—one that mirrors the ethos of these modern CRTs. By a pragmatic estimator, we mean a method that (P1) delivers valid inference under arbitrary within-cluster dependence and size imbalance; (P2) remains computationally stable; and (P3) is implemented in standard statistical software, ensuring analyses are accessible, reproducible, transparent, and directly comparable across trials—facilitating reliable meta-analysis and synthesis.

A. Model-based view. In contemporary biostatistical practice, the prevailing approach to analysing CRTs involves explicitly specifying the VCM. This practice is partially driven by the widespread use of a simplified version of the ICC of the form $\sigma_a^2/(\sigma_a^2+\sigma_\phi^2)$. With reference to the right-hand matrix (2), this ICC formula, required by the CONSORT statement [20], replaces the potentially idiosyncratic main-diagonal elements with a single parameter σ_ϕ , imposing homoskedasticity. Similarly, all off-diagonal elements governing intracluster dependence are replaced with another single parameter σ_a , implying not only known but also identical intracluster correlations—an assumption known as cluster equicorrelation.

Homoskedasticity and cluster equicorrelation are not imposed directly, but instead arise from the choice of model that implies these constraints on VCM. GLME is the common choice with such restrictions on VCM. In GLMEs, the on-diagonal elements of the VCM are implicitly selected by choosing a link function, while a cluster-level random effect determines the off-diagonal elements [15, 16]. For instance, an identity link function assumes homoskedastic errors following a Gaussian distribution (spherical errors); a log link function assumes equidispersion, characteristic of a Poisson distribution. The GLME model is also the starting point for Bayesian approaches in analysing CRTs.

The GLME model makes assumptions about VCM by adding a cluster random effect to a regression equation, thereby introducing an additional parameter to both the regression equation and VCM. An alternative approach that allows direct specification of VCM without altering the regression equation is the GEE model [15, 16]. From the VCM perspective, GEE is fundamentally similar to GLME. However, GEE makes VCM assumptions more explicit by specifying working correlation matrices without changing the regression equation. The most common choice, the exchangeable working matrix, corresponds to cluster equicorrelation, mirroring the assumptions in GLMEs.

While GLMEs are often more computationally tractable—a major reason for their popularity—GEEs offer greater flexibility. For example, autoregressive stationary working matrices can model repeated measures within subjects, assuming correlations decay over time. More complex choices include nonstationary autocorrelation (where temporal

distance doesn't reduce correlation) and unstructured matrices, which place no constraints on within-cluster dependencies [21].

The primary advantage of parametric models like GLME and GEE lies in their potential for statistical efficiency—smaller standard errors through stronger assumptions. This reflects the classical trade-off in the theory of data: one can 'buy information with assumptions' [22]. Yet, as the Law of Decreasing Credibility cautions, greater precision comes at the cost of diminished credibility when those assumptions fail [23, 24].

In CRTs, even when carefully designed, the assumptions required to specify a valid parametric VCM may be neither tractable nor realistic. In pragmatic CRTs—where the correlation structure is unknown—such specifications are not only computationally demanding but often arbitrary. Even when mathematically coherent, these models can become prohibitively burdensome, especially in nonlinear settings where added complexity exacerbates instability.

For instance, the `geepack` package in R explicitly discourages the use of unstructured working matrices due to frequent crashes [25]. These issues stem from discontinuities or flat regions in the objective function, leading to convergence failures—or worse, convergence to spurious solutions, depending on initial values. Validating such models requires exhaustive sensitivity analyses across starting values—often demanding advanced programming and specialised software, which are rarely accessible or used in practice [26].

Moreover, when the primary goal is to estimate the conditional mean function of the regression model, computational stability is essential. Even when the model is correctly specified, issues such as the incidental parameter problem can introduce bias, particularly in nonlinear models with sparse data. This adds a distinct layer of complexity, separate from convergence issues, as it can lead to inconsistent estimates of the treatment effect and, consequently, standard errors, even when the parametric VCM is correctly specified. Due to these computational challenges and lack of convergence, researchers often avoid the complex parametric VCMs needed for validity, opting instead for simpler ones that inadequately represent the underlying dependency.

Although Bayesian methods can offer some relief by regularising estimation through priors, they still require strong assumptions—about both the VCM and the priors themselves. In pragmatic settings, where much of the structure is unknown, these assumptions are effectively arbitrary and can substantially shift results. Similarly, complex estimators like TMLE aim for robustness but involve many modelling and implementation decisions, requiring specialised software and expertise. In both cases, flexibility comes at the cost of analyst discretion, making inference vulnerable to subjective choices.

Ultimately, parametric approaches in CRTs may oversimplify the complex dependence structures in real data. When correlation structures are misrepresented, precision is overstated, and false positives may result. In pragmatic CRTs, this problem is more than technical—it is principled. The true VCM is unknowable, and any specification, no matter how reasonable, is necessarily arbitrary. An apt and often-cited warning is: 'A fragile inference is not worth taking seriously' [27].

These parametric strategies—whether model-explicit (GLME, GEE) or assumption-laden (Bayesian, TMLE)—fall under what is now called model-based inference—an approach that hinges on analysts' modelling choices and their correctness. But an alternative perspective, rooted in the broader quasi-experimental tradition, is design-based inference [28, 29]. This approach shifts emphasis from modelling assumptions to research design, aligning with the Credibility Revolution that has reshaped applied work in economics and other fields [30–34] and earned recent Nobel recognition. It is this design-based lens that we advance in this paper via the CARE protocol.

B. Design-based view. Heteroskedasticity-consistent (**HC**) estimators, or 'robust standard errors,' bypass traditional VCM assumptions by directly estimating the VCM from the data [7]—permitting, for example, arbitrary variances along the diagonal of the left-hand matrix in (1). The original HC0 estimator [7] uses squared residuals but can underestimate uncertainty in smaller datasets when individual VCM elements vary excessively. Subsequent refinements—HC1 (degrees-of-freedom adjusted) to HC3 (jackknife-based)—use weighted residuals to address HC0's

limitations. HC3 is particularly valuable, providing valid finite-sample confidence intervals while maintaining HC0's performance in larger datasets [35].

In GLMs with canonical links, the robust inference framework has shifted emphasis away from goodness-of-fit metrics like R^2 , AIC, and BIC. The priority becomes credible design and stable estimation of the conditional mean. Given a valid mean model and a suitable variance estimator, inference remains valid—unlike in the model-based view, where misspecifying the mean, covariance structure, or (as in TMLE and Bayesian methods) other distributional or structural assumptions can invalidate results.

This principle has many practical implications. For instance, using a log link with HC estimators eliminates the need for negative binomial models to address overdispersion. The robust standard errors effectively handle heteroskedasticity and overdispersion without added complexity, which can destabilise inference [36, 37]. Likewise, Vuong's test for overdispersion becomes irrelevant under robust inference, as it relies on parametric model fit.

Robust inference enables the use of computationally stable link functions across diverse data contexts. Identity and log links, particularly when implemented with modern statistical tools [38], resist challenges like incidental parameters and perfect separation that hinder logit and probit models. For binary outcomes specifically, the identity link yields risk differences and the log link yields risk ratios—the two most directly interpretable estimands on the risk scale—without requiring the constrained binomial likelihoods that often drive nonconvergence in log-binomial models [39–41].

A key trade-off in robust inference is between robustness and efficiency. HC estimators remain consistent under heteroskedasticity and retain full efficiency when errors are homoskedastic, but they do not exploit structure to improve precision. Efficiency depends on the link function's ability to approximate the true conditional variance. In binary models, for instance, a log link may outperform identity by aligning better with the implied error distribution. But more complex links (like logit or probit) may offer only marginal gains while risking computational fragility [42, 43].

HC estimators do not account for dependence among observations (e.g., the within-cluster off-diagonal terms α_{12}^B and α_{13}^B in the right-hand matrix (2)), making them unsuitable for CRTs. To address this, [8] introduced CV estimators, which extend HC methods to allow both heteroskedasticity and arbitrary within-cluster correlation. Like HC estimators, CV estimators permit misspecified VCMs and decouple inference from fit metrics. Under this framework, the ICC is neither clinically interpretable nor needed for inference.

A major strength of CV estimators is their ability to support GLMs with standard link functions while leaving within-cluster correlation unspecified—an approach formalised in Example 1 of [8] and now standard in quasi-experimental research. This avoids the need for computationally demanding models like GLME or GEE, which impose rigid correlation structures. While such structures can, in theory, improve efficiency under correct specification, their adequacy is often questionable in practice—as illustrated by our simulations and case studies below.

Like HC0, the original CV0 can be distorted by influential elements of VCM—whether extreme diagonal values reflecting heteroskedasticity or off-diagonal terms capturing irregular within-cluster dependence arising from unequal cluster size or structure. The CV3 estimator addresses these challenges by downweighting influential clusters and stabilising inference even under pronounced heterogeneity. It delivers improved finite-sample behaviour while remaining efficient in large, balanced datasets, converging to CV0 behaviour. When the working VCM is correctly specified, CV3 standard errors often approximate those from fully parametric models, achieving robustness with limited efficiency loss [9–14, 44–46].

A separate, design-level caveat arises when treatment varies in only a handful of clusters; leave-one-cluster-out quantities can then be undefined, making CV3 inference unreliable [18, 47]. This problem is known in quasi-experimental designs but is ordinarily precluded in CRTs by deliberate treatment replication across clusters. Complementary design-based methods exist within this tradition—bootstrap variants [14, 48] and degrees-of-freedom corrections [13]—but they fall short of our software-nativeness criterion (P3): their implementations are most mature

for linear settings, and extending them to Poisson models (standard in medical research) requires additional tuning that undermines this property.

C. CARE overview. The preceding discussion motivates the CARE protocol’s design-based approach to inference in CRTs, emphasising robustness to complex and often unknown within-cluster correlation.

The initial Clarify step characterises and transparently reports cluster heterogeneity. Rather than relying on aggregate measures like the ICC, it employs well-established deletion diagnostics and cluster-level influence measures (like leverage) to assess individual cluster contributions to variance and dependence. These diagnostics have been recognised and advocated in foundational textbooks for decades [49–51]. Recent Stata and R tools [18] now make them widely accessible, promoting rigour, particularly for unbalanced clusters or smaller trials.

The Clarify step defines how CARE handles missing data—treating missingness not as a technical nuisance to be repaired but as a genuine source of uncertainty to be acknowledged. Imputation may appear to ‘complete’ the data but does so only by assuming that the unobserved behave like the observed—a point long recognised as problematic in applied trial work [52]. Accordingly, CARE analyses data as observed in both Clarify and Apply, accepting that some quantities may be only partially identified yet still informative [24], thereby preserving the integrity of design-based inference.

The Apply step anchors inference in the design. CARE mandates a GLM with identity or log links, paired with the CV3 estimator, and this default applies across continuous, binary, and count outcomes. With continuous outcomes, the identity-link GLM reduces to OLS. With binary outcomes, the identity link yields risk differences, while the log link yields risk ratios (robust Poisson); with count outcomes, the log link yields rate ratios. The link choice is therefore driven by the estimand scale—additive versus multiplicative—not by stronger modelling assumptions: CARE treats the GLM as a working mean model and anchors inference in randomisation via CV3. A practical constraint is that the log link requires a positive conditional mean (so it is used for outcomes on a nonnegative/positive analysis scale), whereas the identity link can also accommodate outcomes that take negative values.

This follows the quasi-experimental tradition, using OLS—or increasingly, Poisson estimators [38]—with robust errors to yield valid inference grounded solely in randomisation. Unlike assumption-heavy alternatives, this step requires no tuning and is implemented in standard software. In doing so it meets the three pragmatic-estimator criteria stated above: (P1) design-anchored validity under complex dependence and size imbalance (via CV3), (P2) computational stability, and (P3) software-nativeness (the jackknife dates at least to the 1950s [53, 54] and is widely implemented in standard statistical software, requiring no bespoke code). Because the same estimator can be applied identically across trials, it also promotes comparability and facilitates downstream evidence synthesis such as meta-analysis.

The Refine step is undertaken only when there is a clear analytic reason to introduce additional structure beyond the benchmark. It covers analyses beyond the CARE benchmark—including assumption-rich approaches such as TMLE, GEE, and GLME (including Bayesian variants)—and does not replace Apply: refinements are interpreted relative to the benchmark and must be reported alongside it. Any refinement must be computationally stable for the realised data.

In practice, Refine is triggered, for example, when one or more of the following holds: (R1) the Apply benchmark is too imprecise to support a decision (e.g., intervals span both clinically important benefit and harm, or cross a pre-specified noninferiority/superiority margin); (R2) the estimand or missing-data structure requires additional assumptions to be interpretable (e.g., imputation or MAR modelling); (R3) a boundary case where fragility is plausible (very few clusters, severe imbalance, or concentrated influence), so that checking alternative methods is particularly informative; (R4) alternatively, efficiency gains are plausibly available because influence is diffuse and the refinement’s assumptions are defensible against what the diagnostics show; (R5) pre-specified trial knowledge supports additional

structure (e.g., stratification or defensible moment/restriction information); or (R6) a pre-registered SAP requires reporting an assumption-rich model for protocol or regulatory reasons.

The Evaluate step synthesises the preceding steps into a coherent inferential conclusion by interpreting any refinements relative to the Apply benchmark. Evaluate requires the analyst to present the Apply benchmark and any Refine results side by side, explicitly assessing whether conclusions are stable across modelling choices. When Apply and Refine agree, Evaluate records this concordance and reports the robust result with confidence (in such settings, refinements are confirmatory and may be omitted without changing the inferential conclusion). When they disagree, the burden of justification falls on the assumption-rich model, not the robust benchmark: the analyst must identify which additional assumptions are doing the work and justify why they are plausible—drawing on the Clarify diagnostics and, where relevant, on pre-specified design or protocol knowledge that influence summaries alone cannot capture.

This sequencing also serves a broader transparency function: even analysts who cannot fully interpret the diagnostics can follow CARE mechanically, and the structured separation of Apply from Refine means that downstream readers and reviewers who can assess the assumptions are able to re-weight conclusions themselves—something that is simply impossible when results from assumption-rich models are presented without a robust benchmark. This mandatory-reporting structure also guards against selective specification searching: refinements may be explored, but they cannot displace the benchmark or obscure the diagnostic evidence about whether their assumptions are credible.

Taken together, these steps reflect a bottom-up approach to modelling: researchers begin with what the data alone can reveal and introduce additional assumptions only when necessary to improve precision or recover otherwise unidentified quantities. This sequencing is particularly valuable in CRTs with very few clusters, where no method is uniformly well-calibrated and the main risk is overconfidence. This approach aligns with the logic of partial identification, Law of Decreasing Credibility, and the broader principles of the Credibility Revolution and design-based inference [23, 28, 29, 55], while remaining consistent with established traditions in the clinical trial literature.

3. CARE application

In this section, we reanalyse data from four published trials to demonstrate CARE. In all cases, the causal estimand—the target quantity for inference—is the average treatment effect between treated and control units. The conditional mean function is assumed to be correctly specified by the known trial design, allowing us to focus exclusively on comparing design-based and model-based inference for this estimand.

A. Case study I. Ten Hoor et al. [56] randomised nine Dutch schools to assess if monthly motivational lessons could increase student physical activity. We replicate their analysis using the publicly available SPSS file and data. For this trial, the outcome of interest is body composition measured as fat-free mass, a continuous outcome.

CARE step I. Clarify: Table 2 reports cluster heterogeneity using the `sumclust` package (R or Stata), which initiates the CARE protocol. Unlike the ICC, these statistics—cluster-level analogues of classic influence measures [e.g., 57]—capture variation that scalar summaries can miss. For methodological details, see [18]; here, we focus on empirical interpretation.

Table 2 reports cluster-level influence measures. With only nine clusters, it is practical to display each cluster individually. When trials include many clusters, such reporting becomes cumbersome; the next case study (in Table 5) shows how these characteristics can be summarised distributionally. The second column of Table 2 shows the number of observations per cluster, ranging from 30 to 149, highlighting substantial imbalance. This raises concerns that clusters may contribute unevenly to estimation and inference.

While cluster size is a basic proxy for influence, it misses deeper sources of variability—hence the need for more refined measures. These advanced influence measures rely on deletion diagnostics—a known yet underutilised

approach in clinical trial analysis, despite being covered in foundational textbooks on GEE [50, Ch. 4.3] and GLME [51, Ch. 9]. These diagnostics evaluate each cluster’s impact by iteratively removing it and assessing changes in estimates, revealing heterogeneity even when clusters appear balanced.

The third (Leverage) column in Table 2 shows how much each cluster affects fitted values by measuring the change in residuals if that cluster were omitted. For instance, the largest cluster’s leverage (2.008) is 5.3 times that of the smallest (0.377), pinpointing clusters that could disproportionately affect fitted values. However, it does not directly indicate influence on specific regression coefficients, such as the treatment effect.

By contrast, the fourth column (Partial leverage) isolates a cluster’s potential impact on the treatment-effect coefficient. It can be read as the weight the estimator assigns to that cluster when estimating the treatment parameter, with nonnegative weights summing to one.

Here, the largest cluster’s partial leverage (0.204) is about 4.2 times the smallest’s (0.049), indicating greater capacity to move the treatment estimate. The final column (Cluster-out effect) shows the estimated treatment effect when each cluster is omitted. Values range from 0.543 to 1.108, a more than twofold difference. For example, dropping cluster 2 yields an estimate of 1.108, while excluding cluster 6 gives 0.543. In some cases, dropping one cluster can reverse the estimated treatment effect on the studied outcome—warranting close clinical and statistical scrutiny.

The table presents cluster-level measures of influence, but our main interest is in their relative values, captured by the coefficient of variation (**CoV**) at the bottom of each column. This provides a single-number summary of cluster heterogeneity, akin in spirit to the ICC but directly tied to how unevenly clusters contribute to the treatment effect. A CoV of zero means all clusters contribute equally (perfectly homogeneous clusters), whereas larger values signal greater heterogeneity. Simulations show that distortions in conventional *t*-tests grow as partial leverage heterogeneity increases [18]. Here the partial leverage CoV is 0.487, indicating appreciable heterogeneity and suggesting that conventional methods should be used with caution.

CARE step II. Apply: Table 3 (row 1) implements one of the CARE benchmarks: an identity link GLM CV3. For comparability, all results reported with cluster-robust variance estimators (CV1 or CV3), two-sided P values and 95% confidence intervals are computed using a *t* distribution with degrees of freedom equal to the number of clusters minus one. As established in Sections 2B, this provides valid inference under minimal assumptions, relying solely on randomisation. The identity link delivers a numerically stable, unbiased treatment effect—even in small or sparse clusters—while cleanly separating estimation from inference. Uncertainty is handled by the CV3 estimator, which avoids the parametric covariance assumptions of the authors’ GLME—where inference hinges on a correctly specified random-effects structure, stable variance-component estimation, and random effects independent of the regressors [9–14, 44–46].

To empirically validate this model for the trial’s structure, we use a placebo regression approach. Originally proposed by [58], this method reassigns placebo treatments across clusters and estimates the treatment effect under the null. Intuitively, it asks: if hundreds of researchers reran this CRT in schools, how often would they find a positive effect even if the treatment had no impact? With nine clusters, there are 126 unique allocations of four treated and five control clusters—enabling us to assess the model’s false positive rate under realistic randomisation.

While not required by CARE, the placebo regression serves as an illustrative check on model robustness. Since placebo assignments are random, the true treatment effect is known to be zero. We focus on the frequency with which models incorrectly reject this null at the 5% level—a threshold aligned with standard public health practice, where excluding zero from a 95% confidence interval is equivalent to a two-sided test.

To evaluate inference quality, we examine how often the null hypothesis is falsely rejected under placebo

Table 2. Cluster complexity in (56)

Clst	Obs per clst	Leverage	Partial leverage	Cluster-out effect
1	30	0.377	0.049	0.688
2	115	1.818	0.162	1.108
3	86	1.132	0.155	0.814
4	44	0.578	0.052	0.966
5	63	1.071	0.094	0.797
6	93	1.207	0.129	0.543
7	67	0.966	0.076	1.064
8	69	0.843	0.079	0.873
9	149	2.008	0.204	0.934
CoV	0.460	0.475	0.487	0.207

Notes: fat-free mass (continuous) outcome from (56). Produced with `summeclust` (18).

treatment—where no true effect exists. A well-calibrated test should yield a 5% rejection rate, reflecting correct Type I error control. Our benchmark model, the identity link GLM CV3, performs accurately in this separate placebo simulation, with a rejection rate of 4.9% across all unique placebo configurations.

CARE step III. Refine: The Refine step in CARE is optional and serves to explore potentially more efficient models familiar to trial practitioners. For illustration, we follow the authors’ original analysis and apply the identity link GLME. This was the model that produced the trial’s headline finding—a statistically significant treatment effect (P value < 0.05, Table 3, row 2) presented as evidence for the intervention’s efficacy.

This example highlights the value of the CARE protocol: unlike the SAP-driven analysis, which assumes a well-specified GLME based on a stylised data-generating process, CARE confronts the actual data structure. By clarifying real-world heterogeneity before modelling, CARE shows why GLME-based inference here may be misleading. Indeed, a placebo regression using the GLME model yields a 62% rejection rate under the null—far above the nominal 5% level—exposing its vulnerability to false positives when its assumptions do not hold.

CARE step IV. Evaluate: Apply and Refine disagree: the robust GLM CV3 finds no significant effect, while the GLME reaches nominal significance. Under the CARE framework, the burden of justification falls on the assumption-rich model. The Clarify step shows this burden cannot be met: the GLME relies on equicorrelation and homoskedasticity, assumptions that the influence diagnostics and placebo simulations show to be clearly violated. The GLME result should therefore be reported with explicit qualification rather than treated as the trial’s headline finding.

Further illustrations: [56] provide additional insights. The authors justified including education level to improve model fit—a rationale grounded in model-based thinking. However, from a design-based perspective, variable inclusion is only warranted if tied to the randomisation process. Fitness alone does not justify covariate adjustment in this context.

Table 4. Additional models applied to (56)

CARE step	Model	Coef or IRR	SE	t/z stat	P val	95% Conf int		Number of		
						lower	upper	obs	clst	
Authors’ model robust SE	Identity link GLME CV3	0.933	0.933	0.537	1.740	0.120	-0.305	2.171	716	9
Alternative recommendation	Log link GLM CV3	0.878	1.023	0.013	1.790	0.111	0.994	1.052	716	9

Notes: Fat-free mass (continuous) outcome from (56). Notes: fat-free mass (continuous) outcome from Ten Hoor et al. (56). Coef = OLS coefficient, IRR = incidence rate ratio, $\partial y/\partial x$ = marginal treatment effect.

Strikingly, as seen in the code, the authors did not include education in their final model, despite citing it. This omission likely reflects a practical barrier: when we include education, the GLME fails to converge. This underscores a common issue in CRTs—pre-registered models may become infeasible post hoc, often for computational reasons. Such breakdowns undermine the premise of strict protocol adherence and highlight the flexibility required in real-world analysis. Even when successfully estimated, the authors’ GLME model fitted with the robust CV3 estimator performs worse than simpler alternatives. As shown in Table 4 (row 1), it returns a higher P value and wider uncertainty than the mandated model from the Apply step, contradicting its theoretical promise of improved precision. In contrast, the simpler log link GLM CV3, fully valid under the CARE framework, delivers better precision with greater computational reliability.

B. Case study II. Tannenbaum et al. [59] conducted a UK-based pragmatic CRT evaluating three continence-promotion strategies for older women with untreated incontinence. We reconstruct their analysis using the trial’s original dataset, focusing on the binary outcome of symptom improvement (‘better’ or ‘much better’) when comparing the combined intervention (workshops + self-management) to control. Regression specifications follow the published methods; analysis code was not available, so we reconstructed the final specification from the article’s description.

CARE step I. Clarify: Table 5 summarises cluster influence measures for this trial. With 34 clusters, we report distributions rather than individual cluster values, unlike in Table 2. While a larger number of clusters might suggest that standard inference is adequate, CoVs across all influence measures are markedly higher here. This makes the example especially informative for CARE: despite 34 nominal clusters, the realised cluster structure provides much less effective information for treatment-effect inference than the raw cluster count suggests. Cluster size varies ninefold, and Partial leverage—a composite measure of cluster influence—shows the largest divergence: the smallest cluster, with a single observation, contributes nothing to the treatment effect, while the largest, with 9 observations, accounts for 12.4%. This degree of imbalance directly undermines simple exchangeable-correlation models that implicitly assume clusters contribute fairly evenly; such models would require much lower CoVs to be plausible.

Table 5. Cluster complexity in (59)

Clst	Obs per clst	Leverage	Partial leverage	Cluster-out effect
Min	1.000	0.070	0.000	0.178
Q1	2.000	0.190	0.009	0.207
Med	3.000	0.355	0.020	0.217
Mean	3.410	0.441	0.029	0.219
Q3	4.000	0.623	0.037	0.226
Max	9.000	1.361	0.124	0.282
CoV	0.650	0.670	1.065	0.085

Notes: Symptom Improvement (binary) outcome from (59). Produced with `summc1ust` (18).

CARE step II. Apply: Table 6 (row 1) reports results from a log link GLM CV3, accommodating the high cluster heterogeneity shown in Table 5. While the identity link with CV3 performed best in a previous trial, here the log link yields greater efficiency, underscoring the importance of empirical evaluation rather than fixed model selection. For this trial, placebo simulations with 10,000 configurations confirm the model’s inferential reliability, yielding a rejection rate of 5.2%, consistent with nominal design-based error control.

There is no universal preference between identity and log link GLMs with CV3. Both are valid for positive outcomes, including continuous or binary measures, while the identity link can additionally accommodate outcomes that take negative values. Efficiency depends on how well the VCM implied by the link matches the data, which can only be assessed empirically.

CARE step III. Refine: At this optional Refine step, we implement the authors’ selected model: a logit link GLM with CV1, which yields roughly a threefold reduction in

Table 6. Application of robust and efficient models on data from (59)

CARE step	Model	$\partial y/\partial x$	IRR or OR	SE	t/z stat	P val	95% Conf int		Number of	
							lower	upper	obs	clst
Apply	Log link GLM CV3	0.245	3.874	2.203	2.380	0.023	1.218	12.321	116	34
Refine	Logit link GLM CV1	0.213	5.986	3.692	2.900	0.007	1.707	20.994	109	34

Notes: Symptom improvement (binary) outcome from (59). IRR = incidence rate ratio, OR = odds ratio, $\partial y/\partial x$ = marginal treatment effect.

the P value compared to the robust benchmark. CARE enables this apparent gain to be critically assessed. The sample drops from 116 to 109 due to complete separation—precisely the kind of computational fragility that (along with the incidental parameters problem discussed in Sections 2A and 2B) hinders logit and probit models. This problem is absent for identity and log links (when estimated via modern tools [60]). In this trial, these issues are compounded by reliance on CV1 in a setting where cluster influence is highly uneven. The partial-leverage CoV from the Clarify step is 1.065, implying that a few clusters dominate the treatment-effect estimate. This is precisely the kind of configuration where CV1 can be badly sized [18]. Consistent with that warning sign, placebo simulations yield a 41% false positive rate—far from the nominal 5%. Unlike a traditional SAP, which would treat this model as definitive, CARE exposes its statistical and computational fragility by situating it alongside robust benchmarks and diagnostics.

CARE step IV. Evaluate: Here the Apply benchmark and the Refine model deliver concordant conclusions, with both indicating a statistically significant and clinically meaningful effect. Evaluate therefore records this agreement and reports the Apply result as the primary inferential statement, since it is design-anchored and requires minimal assumptions. The Refine analysis can be retained as a precision gain and a robustness check, but it is not doing substantive inferential work in this case. This illustrates CARE’s pragmatism: when Apply is sufficient, additional modelling complexity is optional rather than automatic.

Further illustrations: To follow the authors’ steps, we implemented their pre-specified model—a logit link GEE with exchangeable correlation and CV1 (Table 7, row 1). The model failed to converge because it expects relatively

Table 7. Additional models applied to (59)

	Model	$\partial y/\partial x$	OR or Coef	SE	t/z stat	P val	95% Conf int		Number of	
							lower	upper	obs	clst
Authors' mentioned model	Logit link GEE EXC CV1						Computational failure			
Selected model, robust SE	Logit link GLM CV3	0.213	5.986	5.392	1.990	0.055	0.957	37.421	109	34
Authors' preferred assumption	Logit link GLME CV1	0.233	11.262	10.581	2.580	0.015	1.665	76.167	109	34
Preferred assumption, robust SE	Logit link GLME CV3	0.233	11.262	16.323	1.670	0.104	0.590	214.940	109	34
Alternative recommendation	Identity link GLM CV3	0.219	0.219	0.105	2.070	0.046	0.004	0.433	116	34

Notes: Symptom improvement (binary) outcome from (59). Coef = OLS coefficient, OR = odds ratio, $\partial y/\partial x$ = marginal treatment effect.

homogeneous clusters, but the observed data deviated so sharply from this assumption that the resulting VCM was not positive semi-definite [61]. The authors indirectly acknowledged this issue, writing: ‘in cases where an ICC ≤ 0 was detected, we assumed a correlation structure of independence but still used the robust variance estimator.’ Yet they present this workaround as if GEE was still applied, without stating that a simpler GLM was ultimately used. This ambiguity underscores the difficulty of rigid protocols when models collapse under real-world complexity. Such cases highlight the need for frameworks like CARE. Unlike traditional SAPs, CARE enables transparent diagnosis of model-data mismatch and supports principled deviations when pre-specified methods fail.

In Table 7 (row 2) we apply the authors’ likely final model—a logit link GLM—but replace their CV1 errors with CV3. This change eliminates the reported significance, showing the original result stemmed from two issues: a logit link that reduced effective sample size due to computational issues (hurting efficiency) and a CV1 estimator prone to spurious significance under high cluster heterogeneity—even with a relatively large number of clusters.

The authors’ intent to impose cluster equicorrelation with a GEE model could have been implemented more reliably using a GLME, which can be more computationally stable for some datasets. Table 7 (row 3) applies this approach with the authors’ preferred CV1 errors, yielding a statistically significant effect. Replacing CV1 with the CV3 estimator in row 4 eliminates the significance. This contrast illustrates how conventional GEE and GLME models, reliant on equicorrelation or poorly selected error estimators, can produce misleading precision in modern CRTs. Finally, in the bottom row, we evaluate an alternative Apply-mandated model—an identity link GLM CV3 estimator—which again yields statistically significant results. While both the log and identity link GLM CV3 models show significance, the log link offers a slightly better asymptotic approximation in this case.

C. Case study III. Mudge et al. [62] randomised eight wards across four Australian hospitals to test whether an age-friendly improvement programme reduced hospital-associated complications in acute care. We focus on hospital-associated delirium (binary outcome). The dataset and scripts are not publicly available; instead, the original authors ran our requested analyses (matching their primary specification) and shared the outputs.

CARE step I. Clarify: Table 8 presents cluster-level influence measures, illustrating heterogeneity (CoV on Partial leverage is 0.297). Although cluster 7 does not have the largest leverage, omitting it nearly nulls the estimated effect (see the Cluster-out effect column), foreshadowing that a design-based approach may not find a stable effect. The original analysis relied heavily on imputation, whereas the CARE protocol mandates analysing data as observed. Because imputation is inherently model-driven, it conflicts with design-based principles of inference [24]. If imputation is deemed essential, it should be confined to an optional Refine step with explicit justification.

CARE step II. Apply: Table 9 (row 1) implements the log link GLM CV3 model, which handles the small sample size and cluster imbalance identified in Table 8. This robust, assumption-light approach provides a reliable baseline for inference. The resulting incidence rate ratio (IRR = 0.75) was not statistically significant, with a 95% confidence interval of 0.18 to 3.18, which includes the null value of 1. Under minimal design-based assumptions,

Table 8. Cluster complexity in (62)

Clst	Obs per clst	Leverage	Partial leverage	Cluster-out effect
1	84	1.579	0.122	-0.070
2	57	1.228	0.174	-0.067
3	49	1.665	0.144	-0.138
4	49	1.475	0.173	-0.140
5	81	1.271	0.084	-0.081
6	65	1.076	0.074	-0.082
7	63	1.308	0.107	-0.008
8	69	1.399	0.122	-0.012
CoV	0.204	0.141	0.297	0.658

Notes: Delirium (binary) outcome from (62). Produced with `sumclust` (18).

there is insufficient information to reject the null hypothesis, establishing a transparent starting point for more assumption-rich analyses.

CARE step III. Refine: To improve precision, we moved to an assumption-rich, model-based inference step using the authors’ logit link GLME Bayesian model. This approach incorporates thorough imputation (sample size increases from 517 to 559, $\approx 7.5\%$ imputed) and fully specifies the data-generating process, allowing the use of prior information and more complex hierarchical structures. As shown in Table 9 (row 2), the resulting odds ratio (OR = 0.53) is statistically significant, with a 95% credibility interval of 0.31 to 0.90 that excludes the null value. These results indicate posterior mass concentrated on a reduction in delirium, though this apparent improvement depends on additional modelling assumptions.

However, the Bayesian framework demands explicit assumptions about priors, missing data, and correlation structures, introducing risks of subjectivity and variability in results depending on these modelling choices. Unlike a standard SAP, which typically fixes modelling decisions upfront, the CARE protocol highlights how inference can depend heavily on these analyst-driven assumptions, encouraging transparency and systematic reporting.

In practice, full reproducibility of Bayesian analyses remains a challenge. For example, despite extensive efforts, no fully reproducible

Table 9. Application of robust and efficient models on data from (62)

CARE step	Model	$\partial y/\partial x$	IRR or OR	SE or SD	t stat or OR/SD	P val or Tail Prob	95% Conf/Cred int		Number of obs	Number of clst
Apply	Log link GLM CV3	-0.056	0.754	0.459	-0.462	0.658	0.179	3.181	517	8
Refine	Logit link GLME Bayesian	-0.086	0.530	0.271	-2.340	0.019	0.310	0.900	559	8

Notes: Delirium (binary) outcome from (62). IRR = incidence rate ratio, OR = odds ratio, $\partial y/\partial x$ = marginal treatment effect. OR/SD = posterior mean divided by posterior standard deviation (signal-to-noise ratio); Tail Prob = posterior probability that the effect is in the opposite direction.

Bayesian evaluation was publicly available for this paper, illustrating the need for clearer workflows and documentation. CARE thus serves as a safeguard: the robust benchmark model ensures reliable initial inferences under minimal assumptions, while the Bayesian refinement enables more efficient, assumption-rich exploration. This dual approach balances the strength of robust baseline inference with the flexibility and precision of Bayesian modelling, but places a strong emphasis on documenting and justifying all analytic decisions to enhance reliability and reproducibility.

CARE step IV. Evaluate: Apply and Refine disagree: the GLM CV3 yields a small, imprecise estimate with a near-zero signal-to-noise ratio ($z = -0.46$), while the Bayesian refinement reaches nominal significance (OR/SD = -2.34). The burden of justification falls on the Bayesian model, which achieves this sharper signal through imputation, prior specification, and a fully parametric hierarchical structure—each an additional assumption layer beyond what the design alone can support. CARE does not preclude this result, but requires it to be reported as conditional on those assumptions rather than as a straightforward replication of the design-based finding.

D. Case study IV. Kaaya et al. [63] report the Healthy Options CRT in Tanzania, randomising 16 antenatal care clinics to intervention or control. We focus on the continuous PHQ-9 depression score at the second follow-up, and we replicate the authors’ adjusted mean-difference analysis using the publicly available trial data.

CARE step I. Clarify: Table 10 summarises cluster influence measures for the PHQ-9 outcome. Cluster sizes are notably unbalanced (from 9 to 78 observations; CoV 0.635), but the more salient feature is the heterogeneity in partial leverage—the weight each cluster receives when estimating the treatment coefficient. The partial-leverage distribution is highly dispersed (min 0.003, max 0.252; CoV 1.118), implying that some clinics contribute almost nothing to identification while one clinic carries about one quarter of the identifying weight. Even with 16 clinics, the design can behave, for inferential purposes, like a trial with far fewer effective clusters when leverage is highly uneven.

Table 10. Cluster complexity in (63)

Stat.	Obs per clst	Leverage	Partial leverage	Cluster-out effect
Min	9.00	0.139	0.003	-1.379
Q1	16.00	0.235	0.014	-1.177
Med	36.00	0.472	0.029	-1.078
Mean	39.56	0.500	0.062	-1.074
Q3	65.00	0.771	0.091	-1.043
Max	78.00	0.899	0.252	-0.655
CoV	0.635	0.557	1.118	0.175

Notes: PHQ-9 score (continuous) outcome from (63). Produced with `summcLust` (18).

CARE step II. Apply: Table 11 (row 1) reports the CARE benchmark: an identity-link GLM with CV3. This targets the mean difference in PHQ-9 score between arms and uses leave-one-cluster-out jackknife inference. The estimated effect is around a one-point reduction (Coef -1.079), but with CV3 uncertainty the 95% interval includes zero and the P value rises to 0.146. In this 16-cluster CRT, the robust benchmark therefore does not provide evidence that the nine-month PHQ-9 score differs between arms.

CARE step III. Refine: Following [63], we next fit a Gaussian GEE with an exchangeable working correlation and CV1 errors. This reproduces the paper’s reported magnitude closely (Coef -1.022; P value 0.023), and would typically be read as evidence of improvement in depressive symptoms on the continuous scale. However, this refinement relies on additional modelling structure (working correlation and Wald-based large-sample calibration), and its inferential stability must be evaluated against the data’s observed cluster complexity.

CARE step IV. Evaluate: Apply and Refine disagree: the robust GLM CV3 yields a non-significant result (P=0.146), while the GEE with CV1 reaches nominal significance

Table 11. Application of robust and standard models on data from (63)

CARE step	Model	Coef	SE	t stat	P val	95% Conf int		Number of	
						lower	upper	obs	clst
Apply	Identity link GLM CV3	-1.079	0.704	-1.533	0.146	-2.579	0.421	633	16
Refine	Identity link GEE EXC CV1	-1.022	0.402	-2.540	0.023	-1.879	-0.165	633	16

Notes: PHQ-9 score (continuous) outcome from (63).

(P=0.023). The burden of justification falls on the assumption-rich model. The Clarify diagnostics show extreme partial-leverage heterogeneity (CoV 1.118), precisely the configuration where CV1 is known to be badly sized. The apparent significance in the Refine model is therefore fragile and should be explicitly qualified; the CV3 benchmark and its wider uncertainty should be foregrounded when communicating the strength of evidence.

4. Simulation evidence

This section uses a controlled simulation to isolate the impact of cluster size imbalance—an important but underreported feature of CRT data. Unlike previous simulations based on full CRT datasets, this focused exercise highlights the often-overlooked variation in cluster sizes. Most CRT reports provide only the total number of clusters and the average cluster size, masking potentially large differences within clusters. As shown in Table 12, which summarises CRT reviews, a typical CRT includes roughly 20-25 clusters with 30-35 observations each on average. However, detailed distributions of cluster sizes within trials are rarely disclosed [64] and are not explicitly requested by [20]. This omission is critical: for example, two clusters averaging 5 observations each could either be evenly balanced (5/5) or highly skewed (1/9), with substantially different consequences for statistical inference.

Table 12. Typical CRT cluster and sample sizes

	Q1	Med	Q3
Random sample 2000-2008 (n≈278) (1)			
Number of clusters	12	21	52
Observations per cluster	12.5	33.9	88.5
Random sample in 2011 (n=100) (2)			
Number of clusters	15	25	44
Observations per cluster	14	31	94
Cancer studies 2011-2015 (n=118) (3)			
Number of clusters	13	24	54
Observations per cluster	≤10	30	50-99

Notes: Quantiles are computed across trials. A typical CRT has 20-25 clusters and 30-35 observations (participants or repeated assessments) per cluster. Cluster-size distributions are rarely reported, motivating their simulation.

A. Design. We consider CRTs with $G \in \{8, 14, 24, 40\}$ clusters and total sample size $N = 30G$, so the average cluster size is fixed at 30 across designs. A random half of clusters receives treatment ($x_g = 1$) while the remainder serves as controls ($x_g = 0$). The $G = 8$ design (four treated and four control clusters) is intentionally stringent and is included to match the smallest case studies in Section 3 and to reflect CRTs where clusters are large units (e.g., hospitals or wards). Outcomes are drawn from a normal random-effects model

$$y_{gi} = \bar{X}_{gi}\beta + \tau x_g + u_g + \varepsilon_{gi},$$

where y_{gi} is the outcome for individual i in cluster g , x_g is the cluster-level treatment indicator with associated effect τ , \bar{X}_{gi} contains a constant and eight dummy covariates generated with cluster-specific probabilities $\pi_{gk} \sim U(0.25, 0.75)$ for $k = 1, \dots, 8$, $u_g \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.15)$ is a random cluster effect, and $\varepsilon_{gi} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.85)$ is an idiosyncratic error.

Cluster sizes N_g are unequal but sum to N , assigned as

$$N_g = \left\lfloor N \frac{\exp(\gamma g/G)}{\sum_{j=1}^G \exp(\gamma j/G)} \right\rfloor, \quad g = 1, \dots, G - 1, \quad (3)$$

where $\lfloor x \rfloor$ denotes the integer part. The final cluster size is set as $N_G = N - \sum_{g=1}^{G-1} N_g$. The parameter γ controls imbalance: $\gamma = 0$ yields equal cluster sizes, while larger γ induces greater imbalance. This scheme follows [48], adapted here for CRTs. For example, the selected parameterisation fixes the ICC at 0.15 across all scenarios—chosen to reflect values commonly observed in CRTs [2]. We vary $\gamma \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8\}$, which spans balanced designs through severe imbalance (including scenarios with very small clusters).

This setup focuses on the rejection frequency of the null hypothesis $H_0: \tau = 0$ at a nominal 5% level. Because the simulated data contain no true treatment effect, the correct test should reject H_0 approximately 5% of the time, providing a direct check on Type I error control. The GEE IND results reported in Figures 3 to 6 and summarised in Table 14 are based on 100,000 replications per (G, γ) cell; at a 5% rejection rate, the Monte Carlo s.e. is about $\sqrt{0.05(0.95)/100,000} \approx 0.0007$, so simulation noise is negligible at the scale of the figures.

Table 13. CoV, cluster sizes and γ

γ	Obs	Partial	Clusters	
	per clst	leverage	Min	Max
0	0.000	0.009	30	30
2	0.617	0.532	9	79
4	1.104	0.956	2	124
8	1.374	1.183	1	215

Notes: γ induces imbalance, diagnosed by the CoV and the range of cluster sizes.

Table 13 summarises how the imbalance parameter γ governs heterogeneity in cluster sizes and influence. When $\gamma = 0$, clusters are perfectly balanced, with zero CoV, minimal leverage, and 30 observations each. As γ increases, both CoV and leverage rise sharply, and for $\gamma \geq 6$ some clusters shrink to a single observation. These values are identical across designs—whether the design has 8, 14, 24, or 40 clusters—because CoV depends only on the relative size distribution, not on the total number of clusters or observations (which scale together at 30 observations per cluster). This invariance—consistent with step one of the CARE protocol—highlights that inference quality is driven by the degree of imbalance, not by sample size or cluster count alone. In contrast, the ICC—fixed across all scenarios—is blind to these imbalances.

B. Results. Figure 2 plots the proportion of successful model fits (y-axis) against the degree of cluster-size imbalance γ (x-axis), for Stata’s default GEE implementation (normal family, exchangeable correlation)—chosen to reflect the typical applied user’s experience without specialised tuning. When clusters are balanced ($\gamma = 0$), convergence is stable; as imbalance grows, failures rise sharply—at $\gamma \approx 4$, about 15% of runs fail. The problem is far worse with fewer clusters: in additional simulations not shown, none of the models converged for $\gamma \geq 4$ when only 14 clusters were used, and GLME models exhibited similar failures. Because any small-sample correction or refinement requires a fitted model, non-convergence itself becomes the primary bottleneck. Advanced optimisers or custom software can sometimes rescue convergence, but doing so requires programming skill and trial-specific tuning. Even then, these procedures are inherently ad hoc and risk producing unstable or non-reproducible results that are sensitive to the specific rescue decisions made. Identity or log link GLMs provide a stable alternative, avoiding these computational pitfalls entirely.

Figures 3 to 6 display null rejection rates for identity-link GEE models with an independent working correlation, implemented using the `xtgeebcv` package [65], across four cluster counts ($G \in \{8, 14, 24, 40\}$). This package standardises the implementation of small-sample corrections within Stata, ensuring consistent estimation and making these methods accessible to applied users without custom coding. Performance is judged by deviation from the nominal 5% rejection rate, which corresponds to a flat line at 0.05 across all imbalance levels γ . The best

Figure 2. GEE EXC with 24 clusters — convergence

Figure 3. GEE IND with 8 clusters — rej. freq.

Figure 4. GEE IND with 14 clusters — rej. freq.

Figure 5. GEE IND with 24 clusters — rej. freq.

Figure 6. GEE IND with 40 clusters — rej. freq.

Figure 7. TMLE — convergence and rejection rates

Notes (Figure 2): The fraction of simulations where Stata’s native `xtgee` with default settings (normal family, exchangeable correlation) successfully converged. Notes (Figures 3–6): Rejection rates for the null hypothesis (no effect) under normal random effects with escalating cluster imbalance, using Stata’s `xtgeebcv` (65) (normal family, independent correlation). NL = nominal level; MD = Mancl and DeRouen (12); FG = Fay and Graubard (66); KC = Kauermann and Carroll (67); MBN = Morel et al. (68). Stata’s native commands implement CV1 and CV3. Notes (Figure 7): Bars (right axis) show TMLE convergence rates; lines (left axis) show rejection rates under the null (no effect) as cluster size imbalance increases, using a standard R implementation with the `SuperLearner` library.

estimator is therefore the one whose rejection-rate curve stays closest to this line for all values of γ . Because γ controls cluster-size heterogeneity while holding G and N fixed within each panel, robustness requires accurate inference under both balanced and highly unbalanced designs.

Two features in Figures 3 to 6 are especially relevant for very small-cluster CRTs. First, with only $G = 8$ clusters, CV1 becomes extremely anticonservative even under balance (rejecting about 9% at $\gamma = 0$) and its size distortion grows rapidly with imbalance (exceeding 30% by $\gamma = 6$). Second, some bias corrections can become practically unusable at such small G : the MBN correction yields essentially zero rejections throughout Figure 3, reflecting a degenerate (overly conservative) behaviour in this boundary case. By contrast, CV3 and MD remain closest to the 5% line in Figure 3, although neither is exact—consistent with the broader point that inference is intrinsically fragile when only a handful of clusters are available. Importantly, all GEE IND fits converged in these simulations (the convergence indicator equals one for every replication), so the rejection-rate comparisons in Figures 3 to 6 are unconditional and are not confounded by selective non-convergence.

Table 14 summarises these patterns via mean absolute deviation from the nominal 5% level. CV3 is best or essentially tied for best in every design: it is the top performer at $G = 14$ and $G = 24$ and is very close to the best performer at $G = 8$ and $G = 40$. MD is competitive overall, but it becomes markedly conservative at $G = 14$, illustrating that ‘best’ corrections can depend on the cluster count even under the same imbalance mechanism. In contrast, CV1 deteriorates sharply as clusters become fewer and more unbalanced, and MBN can collapse in the extreme $G = 8$ setting. Axis ranges differ across panels to zoom into within-scenario differences (what matters is relative performance for a fixed G), since the degree of size distortion varies mechanically with cluster count. Finally,

we omit CV0: it is the unscaled version of CV1. While CV0 can be reported via `xtgeebcv`, it is not produced by Stata’s built-in commands and, by construction, must reject weakly more often than CV1; we therefore do not report it. We do not report non-robust model-based standard errors for GEE because they rapidly inflate rejection rates, exceeding 60% for most configurations and rendering them unsuitable for inference under minimal data complexity. Similarly, another GEE modification—the quadratic inference function—is also omitted, consistent with theoretical and simulation evidence indicating that its efficiency gains come at a cost to robustness [69].

Because CV3 relies only on fitted residuals, the same conclusion extends to other working-correlation choices and related models. GLMEs with cluster-level random effects or their Bayesian counterparts make stronger assumptions (e.g., homoskedasticity, equicorrelation, and specification of priors) yet still face similar convergence and small-sample issues. In contrast, identity or log link GLMs with CV3—mandated under CARE—deliver stable, assumption-lean inference without custom programming, making them the practical and reliable choice for modern CRT analysis.

Because TMLE is increasingly recommended for CRTs, we ran a dedicated simulation using a common R implementation with `SL.glm` and `SL.glmnet` options, reflecting typical applied usage. Figure 7 shows TMLE convergence (bars) and null rejection rates (lines) as cluster-size imbalance γ increases. Even under perfect balance ($\gamma = 0$), convergence is modest: about 72% with 24 clusters and lower with 14. As imbalance grows, convergence collapses—dropping below 50% for $\gamma > 2$ with 14 clusters and failing entirely for $\gamma \geq 7$. These convergence rates are far worse than those observed in Figure 2, where even at $\gamma = 8$ most models still converge. Moreover, increasing the number of clusters from 14 to 24 yields little improvement in rejection rate behaviour, suggesting that TMLE’s instability is not easily mitigated by modest sample size increases.

Rejection rates behave irregularly: they rise with γ before returning toward 5% under extreme imbalance. This apparent conservatism coincides with very low convergence rates, raising concerns about the reliability of the subset of successful fits. Even if convergence failures were ignored, mean absolute deviation (MAD) in Table 14 shows that TMLE does not outperform the CV3 estimator in terms of Type I error control. This analysis, therefore, reinforces a central concern of this paper: the clinical trial literature’s drift toward computationally fragile, high-maintenance estimators overlooks the need for robust and accessible workhorse models, a gap that the CARE framework is designed to fill with its focus on stable, assumption-lean inference.

5. Conclusion

Uptake of valid, robust methods in CRTs has historically been limited, and the recent shift toward pragmatic designs has coincided with growing advocacy for assumption-heavy, computationally fragile estimators. This trend risks further entrenching poor practice by sidelining simple, reliable tools that already exist and work well. The core problem in pragmatic CRTs is not bias in the point estimate—randomisation protects against that—but overconfidence driven by unexamined covariance assumptions, influential clusters, and fragile computational pipelines.

We propose CARE (Clarify, Apply, Refine, Evaluate): a SAP-ready protocol that puts a design-anchored benchmark first and makes assumption sensitivity explicit. Clarify requires transparent reporting of cluster influence and imbalance using deletion-based diagnostics—leverage, partial leverage, and cluster-out effects—implemented in standard software (`summclust` in Stata and R), rather than relying on the ICC, which is blind to the size imbalance that matters most for inference.

Apply mandates a GLM (identity or log link) paired with the CV3 (jackknife) variance estimator: stable, assumption-lean, valid under arbitrary within-cluster dependence, and available in standard statistical software across continuous, binary, and count outcomes. Refine is conditional rather than discretionary: it covers assumption-rich analyses (GEE, GLME, Bayesian variants, TMLE, randomisation-based checks) when there is a clear analytic motivation—for

Table 14. MAD from 5% nominal level

	Number of clusters			
	8	14	24 ↓	40
CV3	0.0100	0.0105	0.0079	0.0051
MD (12)	0.0094	0.0302	0.0080	0.0048
FG (66)	0.0473	0.0185	0.0182	0.0143
KC (67)	0.0360	0.0202	0.0224	0.0168
TMLE		0.0148	0.0167	
MBN (68)	0.0500	0.0286	0.0285	0.0205
CV1	0.1467	0.0943	0.0583	0.0359

Notes: Mean absolute deviation (MAD) is defined as $\frac{1}{7} \sum_{\gamma=0}^6 |\hat{r}_\gamma - 0.05|$, where \hat{r}_γ is the rejection rate at γ . Lower is better.

example, decision-limiting imprecision, estimands that require additional assumptions (e.g., missing-data structure), boundary-case fragility, or SAP/protocol requirements.

Critically, refinements do not replace the benchmark: they are reported alongside Apply and interpreted relative to it. Evaluate then adjudicates the joint record by presenting benchmark and refinements side by side; when results diverge, the burden of justification falls on the assumption-rich refinement, grounded in the Clarify diagnostics and, where relevant, pre-specified design or protocol knowledge that influence summaries alone cannot capture.

This structure also serves a broader transparency function: analysts who cannot fully interpret the diagnostics can follow CARE mechanically, while downstream readers who can assess the assumptions are able to re-weight the evidence strength accordingly. As regulatory frameworks increasingly accommodate Bayesian methods—including recent FDA draft guidance extending their scope to drug and biological product trials [70]—CARE provides a principled way to integrate them: not as automatic defaults, but as explicit refinements anchored to a design-based benchmark.

This sequencing reflects a broader intellectual shift. Pragmatic CRTs, by relaxing key elements of classical trial design, increasingly resemble quasi-experimental studies—where limited control, structural complexity, and messy data are the norm. The quasi-experimental tradition long ago developed reliable practices for exactly these settings. CARE operationalises those practices within the familiar framework of a trial SAP.

The case studies demonstrate what is at stake in real trials. Across four published CRTs with cluster counts ranging from 8 to 34, Clarify reveals that identifying information is often highly uneven—sometimes so concentrated that a trial with many nominal clusters behaves like one with far fewer effective clusters. Conventional pipelines either fail computationally (e.g., nonconvergent exchangeable-correlation GEE/GLME, separation in logit models, or non-reproducible Bayesian workflows) or deliver fragile nominal significance that evaporates under the Apply-mandated robust benchmark. CARE makes these mechanisms visible before conclusions are drawn.

Our simulations reinforce the same message while separating statistical calibration from computational feasibility. Controlled synthetic designs show that conventional small-sample corrected inference becomes sharply anticonservative as cluster-size imbalance grows, whereas CV3 remains much closer to the nominal level across a wide range of imbalance patterns. Computational instability is not incidental: exchangeable-correlation GEE and mixed-effects models exhibit increasing nonconvergence as imbalance grows, and TMLE convergence can collapse even in moderately unbalanced designs. These failure modes determine what an analyst can actually deliver under a pre-registered SAP.

CARE does not eliminate the intrinsic difficulty of inference with very few clusters or ‘few treated/few control’ designs; no method guarantees exact calibration in such boundary cases. Instead, it provides a robust, transparent default and a structured way to incorporate refinements without restricting modelling choices, while requiring that refinement-driven nominal significance is treated as assumption-dependent unless it is credible in light of the diagnostics and consistent with the benchmark. Embedding CARE into CRT SAPs makes analyses more comparable across trials, discourages overinterpretation of fragile P values, and promotes routine reporting of cluster-size distributions and influence diagnostics. In this sense, CARE completes the pragmatic loop: the operational simplicity of real-world trial design, matched at last by analytical clarity in evaluation.

Extending CARE-style diagnostics to stepped-wedge and other staggered roll-out designs is a natural direction for future work, where recent econometric advances on heterogeneous treatment effects under staggered adoption would be directly relevant [71–73].

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